

Rice dwarf and blast resistance^a of Tetep and Tetep-derived cultivars at Khumaltar, Nepal, 1977-81.

Cultivar	Rice dwarf		Rice blast	
	Diseased seedlings ^b (%)	Degree of resistance	Disease score ^c	Degree of resistance
Tetep	0	HR	0-4	MR
IR1905-8-3-1	0	HR	0-2	HR
IR1416-128-5-8	0	HR	0-1	HR
IR1544-340-6-1	20	R	0-1	HR
IR1905-PPII-29-4-61	10	R	0-1	HR

^a HR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant. ^b Av of 3 replications. ^c 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale 0-9: 0 = no incidence, 9 = 51-100%, Range is for years 1977-81.

identify a single variety resistant to RD and blast (BI), the most serious diseases in the region, to simplify breeding for resistance to both diseases.

Results indicate Tetep and lines derived from Tetep — IR 1905-8-3-1, IR1416-128-5-8 — are resistant. Tetep lines IR1544-340-6-1 and IR1905-PPII-29-4-61 were moderately resistant (disease incidence was 10-12%).

Tetep seems to be resistant to RD as well as to B1 (see table). *R*

Sources of resistance to leaf scald disease

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Leaf scald disease (LSc), caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, commonly occurs in northeast India. Natural disease pressure during wet season is high and offers an excellent opportunity to screen germplasm in the field.

Since 1980, when a varietal screening program was initiated, 741 rice cultivars have been tested for LSc resistance. Few varieties have shown resistance. Of 589 cultivars evaluated in 1980, 24 were resistant. Others were moderately resistant to susceptible (see table). During 1981, 152 cultivars were tested — only 2 were resistant.

Cultivars were field-tested in upland nurseries with high nitrogen (100-60-0) fertilization. Seeds were sown in 2-m

rows at 20-cm intervals. They were surrounded by the local susceptible variety, Mirikrak, which has a susceptible to highly susceptible reaction. *R*

Field reaction of two newly released rice varieties to leaf blast and gall midge in Manipur

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In 1979, Punshi and Phouoibi, new rice varieties developed at the State Rice Research Station, Wangbal, were released in Manipur. Since release, they have almost replaced IR24, and are in about 75% of the areas planted to high yielding varieties (Punshi, 50% and Phouoibi, 25%).

Punshi, formerly KD6-18-7, is a cross between local Phouren (female parent) and IR661-1-140-3-2. It is well adapted to irrigated, rainfed lowland, and transplanted conditions and has moderate drought resistance. It is weakly photo-period sensitive and matures in 138 days. It has outyielded IR24 by 10-15% at 80-40-30 kg NPK/ha.

Phouoibi, formerly KD6-2-1, has similar parentage, adaptability, and resistance. It matures in 135 days, and has outyielded IR24 by 8-12% at 80-40-30 kg NPK/ha.

Before their release, Punshi and Phouoibi were reported to be moderately resistant to blast and gall midge, currently the most destructive local rice disease and insect pest. However, field observations and surveys conducted during July-August 1979 have hinted at high susceptibility to blast and gall

Sources of resistance to rice leaf scald, Shillong, India, 1980-81.

Variety	Score ^a		
	Upper Shillong (1800 m, 245 entries) 1980	Barapani (950 m, 152 entries) 1981	Nayabunglow (800 m, 344 entries) 1980
Paro white	—	1	1
Pokhareli masino	1	1	1
Ciat ICA-5	—	3	1
Colombia-I (73120)	—	—	1
Colombia-II	—	—	1
Aus 173	1	—	—
Carreon	1	—	—
Leng Kwang	1	—	—
PL20 (BG11-11 SEL)	1	—	—
Sail boro 56-2	1	—	—
VL8	1	—	—
Baekgogna	1	—	—
Heug Do	1	—	—
Heug Jo	1	—	—
Heug Jo Do	1	—	—
Ishikari	1	—	—
Kita-Kogane (Yukara/Joiku No. 230)	1	—	—
Nan-ei (Tomoe-Nishiki/Norin No. 20)	1	—	—
Tomoyutaka	1	—	—
Yu-Nami	1	—	—
IR9224-K 1	1	—	—
K333 (Shin-Ei/Rikuto Norin)	1	—	—
Shin-ei (Tomoe-Nishiki/Norin No. 20)	1	—	—
<i>Checks</i>			
Mirikrak (local)	5	7	9
IR36	—	7	7
IR8	7	—	5
China 1039	7	—	—

^aBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale 1-9: 1 = less than 1% (apical lesions), 9 = 51-100% (apical and marginal lesions).

Reaction of Punshi and Phouoibi to leaf blast and gall midge in Manipur, India, 1979.^a

Subdivision	Punshi		Phouoibi		IR24 (check)		Phouren (check)	
	SS (%)	Blast score	SS (%)	Blast score	SS (%)	Blast score	SS (%)	Blast score
Imphal West I	22.04	2-3	26.78	1-4	43.58	1-3	9.60	0-1
Imphal West II	12.71	5-6	14.19	3-4	10.80	3-5	3.92	0-3
Imphal East	32.44	3-4	26.05	1-4	29.32	2-4	6.19	1-2
Thoubal	23.85	4-5	38.33	3-6	23.26	2-6	5.07	0-1
Bishenpur	14.98	3-6	16.89	3-5	9.36	2-4	6.46	0-2

^aSS = silvershoot. Blast score is by the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

midge (see table). Further field observations later confirmed their susceptibilities.

In addition, Punshi is occasionally infected, from nursery to late tillering stage, with leaf scald caused by *Rhyn-*

chosporium oryzae. Standard Evaluation System for Rice (1980) scores range from 3 to 5.

Bacterial blight resistance in donor varieties having other desirable traits

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To isolate a multiple donor variety for bacterial blight (BB), stem rot (SR), brown planthopper (BPH), stem borer

(SB), and blast (BI) for use in the breeding program, 30 desirable varieties were tested for reactions to BB. The experiment was conducted under artificial epiphytotic conditions at Haryana Agricultural University, May-October 1981.

Two 5-m-long rows of each variety were artificially inoculated at maximum tillering. Inoculation was done by cutting 5 cm of the upper leaf portion with

a sickle dipped in a single-isolate inoculum. The inoculum was prepared by soaking small pieces of naturally infected leaves in water for 20 minutes.

Disease reactions were compared 15 days after inoculation. The standard IRTP evaluation (scale 1-9) was used. Disease intensity had reached 9 in susceptible varieties.

BJ 1 and DV 85 showed resistance and appeared to be a suitable donor for BB. Dasal, FR 43B, Mahsuri, IET 4141, Chuigak-45, TKM6, LZN, UPRB 30 and 31, and CB 1 were moderately resistant. Three varieties had intermediate resistance. All others tested were susceptible to BB (see table). These studies showed varieties TKM6 and BJ 1 are resistant to BB. They also have desirable grain character and plant type.

Reaction of various donor varieties to bacterial blight at Karnal, India.^a

Variety	Donor for	Other desirable trait(s)	Reaction to BB ^b
CH 1039	High altitude	-	5
Patnai 23	Salt resistance	Resistant (R) to B1, BS, SB	9
Dasal	Salt resistance	-	3
Getu	Salt resistance	Tolerant (T) of salinity	5
SR 26 B	Salt resistance	-	7
Basmati-370	Salt tolerance, SR resistance	R to BI	7
Jhona 349	Alkali tolerance	-	9
FR 43B	Flood resistance	-	3
FR 13A	Flood resistance	R to SR	7
Mahsuri	Lowland	-	3
Jagannath	Lowland	-	7
Lalnakanda 41	Upland, drought tolerance	-	9
MTU 17	Upland, drought tolerance	-	9
Kataribhog	RTV	-	9
Latisail	RTV	-	9
ARC 6650	BLS resistance	R to BPH, WBPH, RTV	7
IET4141	BB resistance	-	3
Chuigak-45	BB resistance	-	3
DV 85	BB resistance	-	1
TKM6	BB and SB resistance	R to BI, RTV, GLH, BPH, SSB, SR	3
BJ 1	BB resistance	R to BI, BLS, SB	1
LZN	BB resistance	R to BI	3
UPRB 30	BB resistance	-	3
UPRB 31	BB resistance	R to BI	3
IR8	BI resistance	-	7
Carreon	BI resistance	R to BLS	7
Tadukan	BI resistance	R to BLS	5
CB 1	SB resistance	-	3
Siam 29	GM resistance	R to BI, BLS	9
CR94-721-3	GM	-	7

^aBI = blast, BB = bacterial blight, BLS = bacterial leaf streak, BPH = brown planthopper, BS = brown spot, GLH = green leafhopper, GM = gall midge, SB = stem borer, SR = stem rot, SSB = striped stem borer, RTV = rice tungro virus, - = not tested. ^bOn a scale of 1-9: 1 = resistant, 9 = susceptible.

Seedling age and incidence of rice dwarf

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Rice dwarf (RD), the only rice virus disease presently reported in Nepal, is transmitted by the green leafhopper *Nephotettix nigropictus*. RD also occurs in Japan, Korea, and Taiwan.

A greenhouse experiment, conducted at Khumaltar Agriculture Station, Kathmandu, Nepal, in July 1981, examined the effect of rice seedling age on